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To cite this article: Jaroslav A. Hubáček, Lenka Šedová, Věra Hellerová, Věra Adámková & Valérie Tóthová (2024) Increased prevalence of the COVID-19 associated Neanderthal mutations in the Central European Roma population, *Annals of Human Biology*, 51:1, 2341727, DOI: [10.1080/03014460.2024.2341727](https://doi.org/10.1080/03014460.2024.2341727)

To link to this article: <https://doi.org/10.1080/03014460.2024.2341727>

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Published online: 21 May 2024.

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Increased prevalence of the COVID-19 associated Neanderthal mutations in the Central European Roma population

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ABSTRACT

Background: Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) infection and subsequent COVID-19 has spread world-wide and become pandemic with about 7 million deaths reported so far. Interethnic variability of the disease has been described, but a significant part of the differences remain unexplained and may be attributable to genetic factors.

Aim: To analyse genetic factors potentially influencing COVID-19 susceptibility and severity in European Roma minority.

Subjects and methods: Two genetic determinants, within *OAS-1* (2-prime,5-prime-oligoadenylate synthetase 1, a key protein in the defence against viral infection; it activates RNases that degrade viral RNAs; rs4767027 has been analysed) and *LZTFL1* (leucine zipper transcription factor-like 1, expressed in the lung respiratory epithelium; rs35044562 has been analysed) genes were screened in a population-sample of Czech Roma ($N=302$) and majority population ($N=2,559$).

Results: For both polymorphisms, Roma subjects were more likely carriers of at least one risky allele for both rs4767027-C ($p<0.001$) and rs35044562-G ($p<0.00001$) polymorphism. There were only 5.3% Roma subjects without at least one risky allele in comparison with 10.1% in the majority population ($p<0.01$).

Conclusions: It is possible that different genetic background plays an important role in increased prevalence of COVID-19 in the Roma minority.

ARTICLE HISTORY

Received 18 December

2023

Revised 21 February 2024

Accepted 26 March 2024

KEYWORDS

COVID-19; Roma;

polymorphism; ethnicity

1. Introduction

Infection by severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) [causes COVID-19 (COrona Virus Disease – 2019)] has spread world-wide from Wuhan (China) and became pandemic several months after the first case was reported (Coronaviridae Study Group of the International Committee on Taxonomy of Viruses 2020). To date, based on the World Health Organisation database, there have been almost 775 million confirmed cases of COVID-19 and the number of deaths potentially associated with COVID-19 reached 7,000,000 (covid19.who.int; accessed at 16st February 2024).

Several factors, mainly male sex, obesity, hypertension and diabetes lead to the severe disease course (Gao et al. 2021). Several authors also reported significant differences in prevalence and mortality associated with COVID-19 between different ethnic groups (Saatci et al. 2021; Mathur et al. 2021). Among European minorities, Roma communities are under increased risk of being hospitalised with COVID-19 and also have an increased mortality rate from the disease (Holt 2021).

It is well known, that the genetic backgrounds differ significantly between different ethnicities (Huang et al. 2015).

Both susceptibility to the SARS-CoV-2 infection and the course of the COVID-19 could be significantly influenced by genetic background (Ovsyannikova et al. 2020; Clark and Poulton 2020; Colona et al. 2021; Hubacek 2021; Delanghe and Speeckaert 2022; Zhang et al. 2022). For example, among others, variants within genes coding apolipoprotein E, angiotensin 1 and 2 converting enzymes, toll-like receptor 7, different blood groups or HLA types were mentioned in association with COVID-19. It is important to note, that neither common polymorphism (with relatively low OR between 1.1 and 1.5), nor rare variants (as for example within the interferon related genes) with potentially higher impact (Zhang et al. 2022) are able to fully define the risk of COVID-19 clinical outcome and they need to be used in concert with the abovementioned non-genetical risk factors.

Recently, genome wide association studies (GWAS) detected variants at two loci – *OAS1* and *LZTFL1* – transferred to *Homo sapiens* from *Homo neanderthalensis* (Zeberg and

Pääbo 2020; Pairo-Castineira et al. 2021; Zhou et al. 2021) which seem to be of particular importance for COVID-19.

OAS1 (2-prime,5-prime-oligoadenylate synthetase 1, OMIM acc No. 164350) is a key protein in defence against viral infection. It activates RNases which degrade viral (and cellular as well) RNAs. This leads to inhibition of cellular protein synthesis and subsequently to the impairment of viral replication. There is a block of SNPs in very high linkage disequilibrium within this gene and minor alleles are leading to the impaired function of the protein. rs4767027 polymorphism (C→T exchange, C allele detected as risky) is between the variants with the highest potential to influence COVID-19 susceptibility and severity (Zhou et al. 2021; Zeberg and Pääbo 2021).

LZTFL1 (leucine zipper transcription factor-like 1, OMIM acc No. 606568) is strongly expressed in the respiratory epithelium of the lung, predominantly in ciliated cells (Downes et al. 2021). Almost 30 variants within different genes associated with COVID-19 have been detected at 3p21.31 loci using the GWAS, and several studies associated predominantly SNPs within LZTFL1 (located in this region) with COVID-19 (Angulo-Aguado et al. 2022; Rüter et al. 2022; Rescenko et al. 2021; Hubacek et al. 2023a). From the haploblock, we have selected for screening the rs35044562 polymorphism (A→G exchange, G allele detected as risky), which exhibits the most powerful signal in the GWAS. Unfortunately, the specific role of this particular SNP in COVID-19 infection remains so far unexplained in detail.

In our study, we have analysed whether common variants in OAS1 and LZTFL1 loci exhibit different frequencies of genotypes between Roma and majority non-Roma populations from the identical Middle-European region.

2. Subjects and methods

Two groups of subjects were examined and compared. The majority population is represented by the 2,559 individuals

Table 1. Genotype frequencies of two SNPs, transferred to *Homo sapiens* from *Homo neanderthalensis*, in the Czech majority and Roma minority populations.

OAS1	Czech majority		Roma minority		<i>p</i>
rs4767027 Genotypes	<i>N</i>	%	<i>N</i>	%	
CC	1110	44.8	164	55.9	0.0003*
CT	1071	43.3	108	36.9	0.0006#
TT	294	11.9	21	7.2	0.02 [§]
Alleles					
C	3291	65.5	436	74.4	0.0001
T	1659	33.5	150	25.6	
LZTFL1	Czech majority		Roma minority		<i>p</i>
rs35044562 Genotypes	<i>N</i>	%	<i>N</i>	%	
AA	2035	81.5	161	60.5	0.00001*
GA	442	17.7	93	35.0	0.00001#
GG	21	0.8	12	4.5	0.00001 [§]
Alleles					
A	4512	90.3	415	78.0	0.000001
G	484	9.7	117	23.0	

p values are given for *MM vs. +m; #MM vs. Mm vs. mm; [§]+M vs. mm comparisons.

M: major, more frequent allele.

m: minor, less frequent allele.

rs4767027 risky allele – C.

rs35044562 risky allele – G.

(46.5% of males, aged 49.0±10.7 years; BMI 27.8±4.7 kg/m²; fasting glycaemia >6 mmol/l in 11.8% of subjects) from the Czech post-MONICA study (Cifková et al. 2010). Subjects were selected according to the WHO protocol (Tunstall-Pedoe et al. 2003).

Minority Roma subjects (302 individuals; 50% of males, aged 39.2±12.8 years; BMI 29.9±5.6 kg/m²; fasting glycaemia >6 mmol/l in 58.6% of subjects) were selected as described in detail before (Šedová et al. 2015; Adámková et al. 2015).

Samples were obtained after the protocol approval by the joint ethics committee of the Institute for Clinical and Experimental Medicine and Thomayer University Hospital (Docket No. 9877/21G-21-16) and all subjects signed an informed consent for the use of the DNA samples for medical research purposes.

DNA was isolated from buccal swabs. LZTFL1 DNA fragment where rs35044562 polymorphism is located was amplified by oligonucleotides 5' CCT TGG CTC CTG CCA AAT TCC CGC AAT T and 5' AAT TCC TGG GCT CAA GGA ATC CTC TCA CTT CC. PCR product of 249 bp was cut by restriction enzyme Taal. After separation on 10% PAA gel the G allele is characterised by fragments 141 bp + 70 bp + 38 bp and the A allele by fragments 179 bp + 70 bp.

OAS1 rs4767027 was genotyped using oligonucleotides 5' TTT CAC CAG CTA TCT TGG CAC CCT TAG CCC and 5' AAA AGG CAA CAC AAG TGC ATT TTC CAC CC. Uncut PCR product of 151 bp corresponds to the T allele and fragments 121 bp + 30 bp (after MspI restriction) represent the C allele.

Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium and chi-square were used in the analysis using the freely available www tools (<https://www.socscistatistics.com>; accessed 2022/08/15) which are fully compatible with SPSS. A *p* value <0.05 is considered as significant. Genotype and frequencies have been compared in all three models (dominant, co-dominant and recessive) for each polymorphism individually. In addition, we have also compared the cumulative prevalence of alleles identified as "risk" in relation to the COVID-19 disease (categories "0," "1," "2," "3" and "4").

3. Results

Call rates for genotyping varied between 88.1 and 97.6%.

Distributions of genotype frequencies were in Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium for both the majority (*p* values 0.15 and 0.56) and the minority population (*p* values 0.58 and 0.75) for both examined polymorphisms. There were no significant differences in genotype frequencies between males and females within the analysed groups.

Genotype distributions were highly significantly different between the examined ethnic groups (for more details see Table 1).

Between Roma subjects, there were about 40% of carriers with at least one COVID-19 associated risky allele (G) of the LZTFL1 rs35044562 polymorphisms. In contrast, within the majority population, we detected the presence of this allele in only about 18% of subjects (*p* < 0.00001).

Similar, albeit not so extreme, differences were observed in the case of the rs4767027 variant within the OAS1 loci, the Roma subjects were more often carriers of the risky CC genotypes/C allele (*p* < 0.001).

Table 2. Cumulative numbers of alleles associated with increased risk of COVID-19 [based on *OAS-1* (rs4767027-C) and *LZTFL1* (rs35044562-G) polymorphisms] in majority and Roma minority population living in Czech Republic.

	Number of risky alleles									
	0		1		2		3		4	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
MAJORITY	248	10.1	913	37.1	1,059	43.1	226	9.2	13	0.5
MINORITY	13	5.0	63	24.4	118	46.0	58	22.4	6	2.3
<i>p</i>	<0.00001									

If analysed together (Table 2), within the majority population, there are 10.1% of subjects without the abovementioned COVID-19 associated alleles, in contrast with 5.0% in the minority population ($p < 0.01$) and in contrast, only 9.7% of subjects from the majority population are carriers of at least 3 risky alleles in comparison with 24.7% of the Roma subjects ($p < 0.00001$).

4. Discussion

There are several reports mentioning differences in COVID-19 susceptibility and severity between different ethnicities. Our study suggests that the increased risk of COVID-19 in a European minority population, the Roma, could be due to a significant inherited background. Unfortunately, our study is based on genetic epidemiology screening only. We were not able to collect information about the SARS-CoV-2 positivity in our subjects. On the other hand, we have confirmed in other cohorts (Hubacek et al. 2023a, 2023b) that both variants within *OAS-1* and within *LZTFL1* are associated with COVID-19 risk in the Czech majority population.

The genetic differences between ethnicities are well known (Huang et al. 2015) and the genetic screening clearly shows that the Roma subjects are not an exception. Previously we (Hubáček et al. 2020, 2021a) and others (for example Merzah et al. 2021; Soltész et al. 2020) have described significant differences between majority European populations and minority populations of Roma ancestry in genotype frequencies of several potentially medically important variants within different genes. Several reports have traced European Roma populations geographically to India (Rai et al. 2012, Ena et al. 2022). Our results indirectly confirm this finding – the frequency of the minor alleles in our Roma population is almost identical to the frequencies reported for South Asian populations in the 1000Genome project.

Our presented results show the potential importance of *OAS-1* and *LZTFL1* for COVID-19 development.

SNPs localised in *OAS-1* haplotype strongly influence *OAS-1* activity. One of them, rs10774671 polymorphism, is located at the intron-exon junction of intron 5/exon 6 and modifies the splicing site (Sánchez-González et al. 2021). This results in an isoform with higher molecular weight and lower enzymatic activity – this isoform is less efficient against RNA virus infections. Importantly, as the activity of the protein influenced is focused on RNA degradation, this SNP shall be generally clinically important regardless of any further SARS-CoV-2 RNA virus mutation.

Variants within this gene have been associated with COVID-19 in several studies and in different ethnic groups (Banday et al. 2022; Tanimine et al. 2021; Zhou et al. 2021)

and we have failed to find a study describing no effect of this gene on COVID-19. This is also true for the second marker we have examined – within the *LZTFL1* haplotype (Rescenko et al. 2021; Angulo-Aguado et al. 2022; Rüter et al. 2022; Hubáček et al. 2023b), which as mentioned in introduction, can influence lung function. In addition to that, the genomic region where the examined *LZTFL1* SNP is located comprises several other genes whose variants are associated with COVID-19 such as, for example, *CCR5*, *CCR9* or *CXCR6* (Valenti et al. 2021; Hubacek et al. 2021b). Thus the examined SNP could be in strong linkage disequilibrium with other variants and influence the activity of other genes.

Of course, genetic susceptibility to COVID-19 is not limited to these two newly described genes. It is known that there are differences in allelic frequencies of several well-defined COVID-19 associated genes between Roma and majority subjects. For example, frequency of the deletion allele within the *CCR5* gene is higher in Roma from ethnically homogenous communities in comparison to those in the general population (Juhász et al. 2012). Similarly, blood group 0, which is suggested to be associated with lower risk of severe COVID-19 (Pendü et al. 2021), was reported to be present in only 30% of Roma individuals (Bernasovský et al. 1976). Last but not least, the Roma population possesses increased frequency of the *APOE4* allele, but the genotype frequencies of the insertion/deletion polymorphism within the *ACE1* gene are pretty similar to the majority European-derived sub-population (Zeljko et al. 2011).

If there are variability differences in the other genes, with the potential to influence the course and severity of the COVID –19 in this minority, further studies are required.

Importantly, there are potential socio-economic factors (such as, for example, the proportion of population that is uninsured, the number of subjects in the household or using public transportation) (Lamb et al. 2021), as well as distinct ways of living (Armitage and Nellums 2020; Mishra et al. 2021), which could partially explain such differences, but the major part of the differences remains hidden. However it should be mentioned that the prevalence of both obesity as well as diabetes, as two major risk factors for COVID-19, is also much higher in Roma subjects (Zajc Petranović et al. 2021).

We are aware of the limitations of our study. Firstly, we lack the confirmatory group and the numbers within the groups are relatively uneven. We also have a relatively low genotyping call rate for one examined SNP in a minority group. Nevertheless, the observed differences between the groups are so obvious, that we don't expect them to affect these differences significantly. Finally, as we have used the retrospectively collected DNA biobanks, we have no

information on SARS-CoV-2 positivity in our subjects – thus we cannot exclude the rather unlikely possibility that the alleles described as “risky” in previous studies (Banday et al. 2022; Tanimine et al. 2021; Zhou et al. 2021; Rescenko et al. 2021; Angulo-Aguado et al. 2022; Rüter et al. 2022; Hubacek et al. 2023a, 2023b) performed on European majority populations may in fact have no or even the opposite effect on COVID-19 in the Roma population. However, this possibility is unlikely, especially in the case of the *OAS-1* polymorphism, where the functionality of the polymorphisms is clearly described (Sánchez-González et al. 2021).

Genetic analyses represent a simple, available and cheap possibility to distinguish subjects at increased risk of COVID-19 and can be used in the future as an important tool for timely detection of subjects with increased risk of SARS-CoV-2 infection and or COVID-19 course and severity.

The fact that the frequency of COVID-19 associated alleles within the Roma minority population is increased, shall not be disregarded and ignored.

Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the author(s).

Funding

The study was supported by the project Ministry of Health Czech Republic – conceptual development of research organisation (“Institute for Clinical and Experimental Medicine – IKEM, IN 00023001”) and by the project National Institute for Research of Metabolic and Cardiovascular Diseases (Programme EXCELES, ID Project No. LX22NPO5104) – funded by the European Union – Next Generation EU.

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Data availability statement

Anonymised results generated during the study are available from corresponding author on reasonable request.

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